

CDE-Mapper: Using retrieval-augmented language models for linking clinical data elements to controlled vocabularies

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ABSTRACT

The standardization of clinical data elements (CDEs) aims to ensure consistent and comprehensive patient information across various healthcare systems. Existing methods often falter when standardizing CDEs of varying representation and complex structure, impeding data integration and interoperability in clinical research. This paper presents CDE-Mapper, a framework that combines a retrieval-augmented generation strategy with large language models to automate the alignment of CDEs with controlled vocabularies. Our modular approach features query decomposition to manage varying levels of CDEs complexity, integrates expert-defined rules within prompt engineering, and employs in-context learning alongside multiple retriever components to resolve terminological ambiguities. In addition, we propose a knowledge reservoir validated by a human-in-loop approach, achieving accurate concept linking for future applications while minimizing computational costs. For four diverse datasets, CDE-Mapper achieved an average of 7.2% higher accuracy improvement compared to baseline methods. This work highlights the potential of advanced language models in improving data harmonization and significantly advancing capabilities in clinical decision support systems and research.

1. Introduction

In the digital era of healthcare, the strategic use of data from electronic health records (EHR), clinical trials, and observational studies is pertinent to advance clinical research and improve healthcare outcomes [1]. However, the potential of these data is frequently not realized due to significant challenges in data standardization and integration across diverse healthcare systems [2]. An important issue is inconsistent representation and interpretation of clinical concepts across datasets, which requires the use of concept linking. Concept linking is the process of aligning clinical data elements in controlled vocabularies to achieve semantic consistency across systems. This task is also termed entity linking and entity normalization of clinical/biomedical labels.

Several studies have highlighted the risks associated with poor concept linking. For example, Abigail et al. [3] identified significant discrepancies between patient cohorts defined by ICD-10 codes and those confirmed by laboratory results, while Hardy et al. [4] reported substantial inconsistencies in the recording of ICD-10 codes in conditions such as autism, diabetes, and Parkinson's disease. These findings highlight the broader challenge of inconsistent concept linking

practices, which impede accurate data integration, reproducibility in research, and reliable healthcare decision making. Although no system can entirely eliminate such discrepancies, improved concept linking methods can reduce inconsistencies, and enhance interoperability across datasets.

Clinical data elements (CDEs), whether atomic (representing a single characteristic) or composite (capturing multiple interdependent attributes), are foundational to clinical data documentation. Although atomic CDEs can be mapped to established terminologies, composite CDEs introduce additional complexities due to the relationships among attributes (e.g., biomarkers with different measurement methods over time, history of disease pertaining to a family member). The composite representation of CDEs is often not considered adequately in the concept linking task [5–9]. A systematic and rigorous approach is required to harmonize these data elements in heterogeneous datasets, ultimately enabling accurate interpretation, transparency, integration, and secondary reuse of health data.

Many studies have explored methods to address the prevalent issue of CDEs standardization in the healthcare domain. Existing approaches

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range from recurrent neural networks to more advanced deep neural models [10,11], including fine-tuned language models such as bidirectional encoder representations of transformers (BERT) [12], which can analyze both free text and tabular data [8,9]. In particular, ensemble methods [13], further refined through fine-tuning for free text (e.g., clinical notes), have been investigated. Traditional rule-based systems such as QuickUMLS [14], MetaMapLite [15] and cTAKES [16] have been proposed. Despite these advances, many existing approaches are optimized for atomic CDEs and are therefore less effective in standardizing composite CDEs. Additionally, the scalability of these methods is challenged by the need to process large controlled vocabularies, as well as handling overlapping and granular concepts.

Large language models (LLMs), also known as generative models, are a class of artificial intelligence models designed to understand and generate human-like text based on vast amounts of training data [17,18]. LLMs can capture complex language patterns and contextual relationships in data from various modalities [17,19]. They have been widely used in natural language processing tasks such as text generation, translation, summarization and question answering, demonstrating their versatility and effectiveness in handling diverse linguistic challenges [17,19,20]. However, LLMs generally lack intrinsic domain knowledge unless they are fine-tuned or augmented with domain-specific resources [21]. This limitation becomes apparent in clinical data standardization, where specialized terminologies, varying data representations and large, evolving controlled vocabularies pose significant challenges [20].

To address these challenges, existing research has explored zero-shot learning [22] and schema-guided prompts [23], enabling LLMs to align extracted information with structured knowledge bases even in the absence of task-specific training data. In particular, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) has emerged as a promising technique [21,24], as it combines the generative capabilities of LLMs with non-parametric memory (an external resource) to dynamically retrieve relevant domain-specific knowledge [25]. By accessing large, frequently updated controlled vocabularies on demand, RAG ensures that concept linking remains accurate, up-to-date, and better aligned with the multifaceted requirements of clinical data standardization. This ability to seamlessly integrate external knowledge makes RAG particularly well suited for handling complex or evolving terminologies, which is central to our approach.

In this work, we introduce a RAG model that tackles two major challenges: (1) inconsistent representation of terminologies across data dictionaries and (2) the inherent complexity of composite CDEs. Our approach surpasses existing baselines by comprehensively standardizing both atomic and composite CDEs, addressing key limitations not fully resolved in prior studies [26–28]. Specifically, we handle varying levels of granularity and dependency in CDEs, overlapping terminologies and the integration of large-scale knowledge bases for enhanced concept linking. To achieve this, we developed a modular RAG architecture comprising query decomposition, ensemble retrieval, knowledge filtering, and a knowledge reservoir. Critically, our knowledge reservoir incorporates a validation mechanism to verify mapped concepts before storing them for future use, ensuring scalability for real-time applications. This validated modular design distinguishes our approach from existing solutions by offering a more robust framework for accurate and efficient standardization of CDEs.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the background and related work, Section 3 presents our methodology and proposed framework, Sections 4 and 5 detail the experimental setup and results, Section 6 provides interpretation of results and discusses the limitations and Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. Background and related work

2.1. Clinical Data Elements (CDEs)

Clinical Data Elements are the fundamental building blocks of healthcare information, describing patient demographics, diagnoses,

and laboratory tests [29]. These elements reside in data dictionaries that provide metadata such as data types, permissible values, associated attributes, and definitions. Standardization of CDEs involves linking them to controlled vocabularies (e.g., ICD-10, SNOMED CT), ensuring consistent interpretation and interoperability between disparate systems [30]. As illustrated in Fig. 1, CDEs vary in their representation and structure:

- Atomic CDEs represent a single characteristic (for example, ‘sex’ or ‘blood group’). Even seemingly simple CDEs can be encoded differently (e.g., M/F vs. 0/1), leading to inconsistencies if not harmonized.
- Composite CDEs include interdependent or hierarchical attributes, for example, a family history entry that documents both the specific diagnosis and details about the affected family member. A pertinent example of dependent CDEs is biomarkers, which are measured at specific intervals using different techniques. These composite structures add layers of complexity because multiple attributes must be accurately assigned to standardized terminologies [31].

Accurate representation of these CDEs, especially composites, is vital for downstream tasks such as data integration, clinical analytics, and AI-based clinical decision support.

2.2. Controlled vocabularies

One effective approach to ensure consistent representation of CDEs is the adoption of Common Data Models (CDM) and their associated controlled vocabularies. CDMs aim to mitigate the challenges of heterogeneity in healthcare systems by defining standardized data structures and terminologies. The most prominent open-source CDMs, such as FDA Sentinel [32] and OMOP [33], vary in their support of structural and semantic standardization. Among these, the OMOP Common Data Model [34], developed by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community, is increasingly used to structure and standardize observational health data in various clinical and research settings [35].

In OMOP, data are organized into a person-centric relational database format that captures a wide range of clinical domains: including medical conditions, procedures, medications, healthcare visits, events, devices, demographics, and family history [33,34]. Central to OMOP’s adoption is its extensive use of controlled vocabularies, which maintain terminological consistency across studies. By mapping CDEs to these vocabularies, researchers and clinicians can align different data sources more easily. This alignment facilitates transparent reporting and enhances the reproducibility of predictive models.

In this work, we have leveraged a knowledge base of more than three million concepts from controlled vocabularies such as SNOMED, LOINC, ICD, ATC, MedDRA, RxNorm/RxNorm-Extension, MeSH, UCUM, OMOP Extension, and OMOP Genomic. These vocabularies provide standardization for various clinical data domains mentioned above [36]. The widespread adoption of these controlled vocabularies also improves the reproducibility of our work and facilitates data sharing within the broader research community, which is crucial to advance medical knowledge and predictive modeling [37–39].

2.3. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)

For effective linking of CDEs in controlled vocabularies, there is still a pressing need for dynamic and context-aware methods. Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) models meet this need by combining pre-trained parametric knowledge with dynamically retrieved non-parametric information [21,40]. It enables language models to generate more accurate and contextually relevant responses [21,24]. This approach is particularly effective for addressing an LLM’s limitations,

Fig. 1. Atomic and composite terms in four clinical data elements (sex, heart stroke, eGFR, and FHH). Each CDE is described by its common label, encoding datatype (e.g., int), nature (e.g., discrete or continuous), associated unit, visit, method and/or formula.

such as hallucinations and difficulty accessing specific background knowledge, especially when working with specialized domains such as clinical data [21,24,25].

In-context learning, a technique that allows models to adapt to new tasks by leveraging examples embedded directly in the input prompt, further enhances the capabilities of RAG systems [41]. The efficacy of in-context learning depends on the quality of the training examples provided; specifically, the relevance and diversity of these examples are critical factors that determine the model’s performance during inference [42,43]. Recent methods have focused on optimizing the selection of examples to maximize the effectiveness of in-context learning. Relevance-based approaches [44] prioritize examples aligned with the input query, while techniques like k-nearest neighbor prompting [45] identify semantically similar examples from a predefined set. Similarly, advancements in the RAG architecture include a modular approach that allows flexible customization, optimization of the retrieval, and generation components [21,25]. Other approaches prioritize dense retrieval using semantic embeddings or sparse retrieval using keyword-based matching or graph-based methods [46].

2.4. Embedding models

Transformer-based embedding models [47] create rich semantic spaces that are crucial to retrieving relevant information in RAG systems. By converting text into high-dimensional vectors that capture latent semantic features, these models leverage pre-trained knowledge – further refined through fine-tuning – to anchor and interlink biomedical concepts. In this vector space, semantically related terms cluster together, facilitating efficient retrieval based on spatial proximity [48].

However, models trained on general corpora often fall short of accurately representing specialized clinical/biomedical terms. To address this gap, self-alignment pretraining techniques, such as SapBERT [26] tailor embedding spaces specifically for clinical and biomedical entities. By minimizing contrastive loss, SapBERT draws semantically similar entities closer, thereby improving precision in identifying relevant medical information. Sparse embedding models such as SPLADE [49] offer an additional layer of keyword-level matching, complementing

dense embeddings in biomedical retrieval tasks where string match **suffices** for concept linking. Within RAG systems, these refined embeddings enable more effective retrieval by mapping queries to the most contextually relevant medical concepts in controlled vocabularies, thus enhancing both accuracy and specificity in concept linking.

2.5. Related work

One common approach to concept linking is representation via lookup tables, such as the UMLS browser and rule-based systems that can capture semantic lexicons to identify concepts in text, including cTAKES [16], MetaMap [15] etc. Recent advances in machine learning, deep learning [10], and LLMs have significantly improved the performance of concept linking. In recent years, many deep learning-based methods have been proposed, including single neural network-based, multitask learning-based, transfer learning-based, and hybrid model-based methods. These methods have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in identifying clinical/biomedical concepts from various datasets; however, they have a significant limitation in scalability due to a limited training dataset [50].

Song et al. [51] and Yan et al. [52] proposed representation learning models that leverage synonyms and hypernyms to link biomedical concepts in scientific literature and social media data. Additionally, unsupervised and self-supervised learning approaches are explored for concept linking in biomedical literature and social media datasets, eliminating the need for task-specific supervision. These methods align the representation spaces of biomedical concepts using scalable metric learning frameworks and have shown promising results on several benchmark datasets of medical concept linking [26,53]. SapBERT [26] refines embeddings for biomedical concepts through self-alignment pre-training, improving the precision of concept identification. Similarly, KRISS BERT [28] and BioBERT-snomed [54] have been fine-tuned for biomedical text to enhance entity recognition and linking tasks by incorporating additional context and integrating concept hierarchies, respectively. Another work proposed a two-stage concept linking model that used in-context learning to address the challenge of ambiguous mentions [55]. Researchers have utilized the structural

information of the knowledge graph through knowledge graph embedding to link concepts effectively. In another study, the potential of multilingual bi-encoder models is explored, including various fine-tuned BERT models in the medical domain, highlighting the challenges of linking domain-specific language concepts [7].

Most of the aforementioned methods for concept linking face challenges related to generalization and limited training data, leading to decreased accuracy when applied to unseen data during inference. Approaches that utilize prompt learning and context-aware representation learning primarily focus on free-form text, such as clinical notes [55–57]. However, recent advances in LLMs, such as GPT [58] and Llama [59], have enabled the automation of concept linking for unseen data of different modalities through in-context learning and the integration of external knowledge using RAG [60–62]. In this context, few initiatives have leveraged LLMs for concept linking, as demonstrated by [27,63], which specifically target atomic CDEs.

Another work, SPIRES [23], proposed structured data extraction from unstructured text and its linking to controlled vocabularies. Although conceptually aligned with our query decomposition methodology, SPIRES focuses on extracting entities and linking atomic concepts from text. However, these solutions prove inadequate when confronted with a vast retrieval space that includes multiple vocabularies and overlapping but semantically distinct concepts. Moreover, these approaches fail to address scenarios where each data element may embody a composite structure, necessitating linking to multiple concepts to establish a cohesive link.

In contrast, our framework extends these principles to structured data by addressing concept linking for various clinical data representations, including atomic CDEs, dependent CDEs, and composite CDEs. Our approach is designed to handle linking across multiple controlled vocabularies simultaneously, leveraging an RAG system with modular components, including query decomposition, ensemble retrieval, and a knowledge reservoir. Given their demonstrated superior performance on concept linking tasks compared to alternative methods, SapBERT [26], KRISS BERT [28], and BioBERT-snomed [54] are widely adopted and well-established baselines for evaluating our approach.

3. Methods

The task of linking CDEs to controlled vocabularies involves defining a healthcare data dictionary, denoted D and a biomedical knowledge base, denoted as KB . The data dictionary D is structured as a table, where each row corresponds to a distinct variable from the underlying dataset. The columns in this data dictionary provide metadata for each variable, such as variable label, data type, its scale type (e.g., continuous, nominal, or ordinal), measurement unit, formula, visits, and other relevant details [64]. This horizontal structure highlights the attributes of each variable, with each row representing a specific variable and its associated metadata, which describes its properties. The primary objective of this task is to establish links between the elements of D and the corresponding concepts in KB , thereby facilitating the harmonization of data across various data sources. In this context, clinical data dictionaries provide metadata that describes clinical records, including field names, attributes, and values, to support the contextual standardization of data elements using controlled vocabularies. The **Data Dictionary** D can be formally defined as a set of tuples:

$$D = \{(M_i, L_i, E_i) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

Each tuple (M_i, L_i, E_i) contains the following elements:

- M_i : The name of a variable.
- L_i : The label (description) associated with M_i .
- E_i : Additional metadata related to M_i (e.g., type, measurement units, formula, and categories).

The **Knowledge Base** KB is structured as:

$$KB = (C, S, T, H)$$

where:

- C : Controlled vocabulary terms or concepts, e.g., Acute Myocardial Infarction.
- S : A set of synonyms, each uniquely assigned to a concept in C , e.g., AMI, Acute Myocardial Infarction.
- D : Semantic types, e.g., medical condition, procedure.
- H : Hierarchical relationships between concepts, represented as pairs (c_1, c_2) , where c_2 is a parent term of c_1 , e.g., Acute Myocardial Infarction is an acute ischemic heart disease.

The goal of concept linking is to identify the terms in KB that correspond to the elements in D . Specifically, for each label L_i and E_i in D , there should exist corresponding description(s) C_l and C_e in KB such that the term(s) in C_l and C_e accurately represent L_i and E_i , respectively.

3.1. Datasets

For this study, we used four diverse datasets with varying characteristics to ensure a comprehensive evaluation and robust results. These datasets include the BC5CDR-Disease corpus [65], the National Center for Biotechnology Information Disease Corpus (NCBI-DC) [66], the MIMIC-III-iBKH-Disease dataset (MIID) [27], and the data from Heart Failure (HF) studies, specifically the Trial of Intensified versus Standard Medical Therapy in Elderly Patients with Congestive Heart Failure (TIME-CHF) [67] and the Chronisch Hartfalen ESC-richtlijn Cardiologischepraktijk Kwaliteitsproject Hartfalen (CHECK-HF) [68]. Ethical approval for CHECK-HF was provided by the Ethical Committee of the Maastricht University Medical Center, the Netherlands and for TIME-CHF by the Ethical Committee of Both Basel (EKBB), Switzerland.

We extracted all relevant information from these datasets into a data dictionary using the methodology described in BioSyn [69]. In particular, only the HF dataset contained composite CDEs, allowing us to assess the effectiveness of our method in handling more complex clinical data structures. Table 1 summarizes key characteristics of these datasets, including source, size, annotation type, total entities, unique concepts and presence or absence of composite CDEs.

Where available, datasets mapped to UMLS Concept Identifiers were further linked to OMOP IDs following the procedure described by [70]. The diverse nature of these datasets, spanning biomedical literature to clinical records, enabled a comprehensive evaluation of our proposed method across different types of medical concepts.

3.2. Proposed framework

As shown in Fig. 2, the overall framework orchestrates a stepwise process incorporating an LLM and a multi-tier retrieval strategy to ensure precise and clinically relevant concept normalization. As described in Section 3.1, we standardize the input format to a data dictionary comprising columns such as description, categories, measurement units, formulas, and visits. All inputs are structured in this format, the description of variable is mandatory, while other components are optional. During query decomposition, examples are selected based on contextual relevance to each input. These examples guide the model in the decomposition task.

In the next step, query decomposition breaks down composite queries into simpler and manageable components. Then each component is individually processed. In the knowledge retrieval component, the algorithm employs a stack of retrievers to find the most accurate match within a knowledge base. Then a knowledge filtering method is applied to retrieve relevant candidates based on a threshold t_s for contextually appropriate selection. If an exact match is found, the term

Table 1
Summary of datasets used in this study.

Dataset	Source	Total mentions	Unique concepts	Concepts type	Composite CDEs
BC5CDR-disease	PubMed articles	73,126	1247	Diseases	No
NCBI-DC	Biomedical literature	73,024	359	Diseases	No
MIID	MIMIC-III linked to iBKH-Diseases	1493	1493	Diseases	No
HF studies	TIME-CHF,CHECK-HF	476	476	Demographics, Diseases, Procedures, Visits, and Measurements	Yes

Fig. 2. Modular framework stepwise workflow for concept linking of common data elements using RAG.

is added directly to the result list N . If no exact match is found, the two-step ranking module is triggered to find the most contextually relevant candidate. Finally, correctly predicted concepts are stored in the knowledge reservoir through a human-in-the-loop approach, where experts validate the final mappings to ensure accurate clinical interpretation before retaining them for future use.

To further illustrate the detailed workflow of the framework, Fig. 3 provides an example-driven flow chart that shows the stepwise integration of query decomposition, ensemble retrieval, and modular components with input sample data. This detailed representation highlights how the framework standardizes the input format, processes components individually and links them to unique standard concepts using JSON as an output schema. The structured output (e.g., JSON) with expected schema components, where the base entity, associated concepts, categorical values, measurement units (if available) and so on are individually linked to unique standard concepts. We chose the specific JSON completion format because it provides a standardized hierarchical structure that aligns well with the complexity of clinical CDEs. This format ensures consistency in the decomposition of composite queries, supports optional attributes and simplifies linking to standard terminologies. JSON's compatibility with downstream systems (e.g., OMOP, FHIR), its interpretability for quality assurance, and its scalability for future extensions make it an optimal choice.

The process of normalizing medical concepts within the CDE-Mapper framework is detailed in Algorithm in Appendix. It outlines the step-by-step process of decomposing queries, applying retrieval methods and using relevance ranking to ensure precise normalization of healthcare data. Each component is described in detail in the following subsections.

3.2.1. Knowledge base creation

In this study, we enhance each concept within selected controlled vocabularies by systematically expanding its set of similar terms. First,

we remove duplicate or redundant synonyms within the same vocabulary, similar to eliminating stop words in text processing. Next, we incorporate additional synonyms drawn from mapped vocabularies, guided by equivalence relationships (e.g., “Maps to” or “Trade name”). For example, if an ATC concept is related to an equivalent RxNorm concept, synonyms of RxNorm concept are merged into the ATC concept terminology set.

Furthermore, in vocabularies with flat hierarchies (e.g., UCUM), the concept codes are aligned with textual labels, so that both forms are recognized as equivalent terms (e.g., mm [Hg] and millimeter mercury column). Table 2 illustrates the representation of the concept in the selected vocabularies before and after the addition of synonyms using this approach.

This expansion of synonyms offers greater terminological coverage and stronger contextual grounding for data standardization. By capturing the various ways each concept may appear in clinical or research data, the enriched vocabularies facilitate more accurate mapping and improve overall retrieval performance within embedding-based systems.

3.2.2. Linking rules

The linking rules provide a structured and dynamically configurable approach for linking clinical terms to appropriate source vocabularies based on data types. For example, consider a patient's record indicating a diagnosis of “heart attack/MI” alongside related medications and lab results. The linking rules would be as follows:

- Link the condition “heart attack/MI” to a standard vocabulary term from SNOMED CT.
- Link prescribed medications, such as “Carvedilol 3 mg twice daily”, to the corresponding RxNorm identifier. In cases where drug information is less specific, such as “Carvedilol” without

Fig. 3. Detailed overview of proposed modular RAG framework for normalization and linking CDEs in controlled vocabularies (e.g., SNOMED, LOINC, ATC, RxNorm).

dosage details, where a broader classification is sufficient, the ATC classification may be used.

- Laboratory measurements, such as “Troponin.T levels”, are linked to the appropriate LOINC or SNOMED code.

Additionally, contextual factors such as prevalence and incidence are also considered. For example, if a patient’s record mentions a “history of myocardial infarction”, the system interprets this as part of the patient’s baseline information. Consequently, the rule implies mapping this historical context to a specific concept denoting a past condition rather than an active diagnosis, reflecting its significance in the patient’s medical history. In our example, the historical context of the disease informs the concept linking process to differentiate between current and past conditions, preventing misclassification. Employing these flexible rules not only enhances the efficiency of clinical data extraction but also allows the process to adapt to meet specific research requirements. For example, researchers who examine the progression of disease over time can rely on accurately linked concepts to identify patient cohorts, treatment regimens, and outcomes, thereby facilitating more robust and insightful analyses.

3.2.3. Query decomposition

The query decomposition module serves two key functions: (1) enhancing the quality of the original query and (2) decomposing the query

Table 2
No. of concepts with synonyms per vocabulary.

Vocabulary	Total concepts	Initial concepts with synonyms	Updated concepts with synonyms
SNOMED	385 573	187 040	381 981
ATC	6379	446	6153
ICD9	10 648	668	10 406
ICD10	289 385	19 322	288 409
LOINC	216 441	2861	168 068
MeSH	334 573	19 841	22 577
MedDRA	69 041	0	63 556
RxNorm	206 239	445	185 695
RxNorm extension	1 923 788	0	1 846 835
UCUM	1012	1	1012
OMOP extension and OMOP genomics	382 566	3349	380 797

into a structured completion format. This process outputs a structured format (e.g., JSON), where each component is treated as a subquery. Formally, it can be expressed as:

$$G_{\theta}(x) \rightarrow (s, Q)$$

where x is the original query, s is the refined query and $Q = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n\}$ represents the set of decomposed sub-queries, with each subquery q_i corresponding to a specific component of the structured format, such as label, categorical values, unit, method, or formula. The decomposition divides each relevant component into its own subquery. An effective implementation of G_θ leverages an in-context learning prompt-based strategy using task descriptions, original queries, and relevant examples to guide an LLM.

To address domain-specific data extraction, we collaborated with domain experts to curate high-quality examples, thereby enhancing the robustness and adaptability of the decomposition process. For simple queries with a single variable, the base entity is treated as a standalone subquery without further decomposition. Consider an original query: “heart attack—main-cause of hospitalization, measured at baseline, categories include 0 = No, 1 = Yes, 9 = Missing”. The decomposition process involves breaking this query into a structured format, such as:

Decomposition Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{base_entity: "heart attack",} \\ \text{associated_entities: ["Hospitalization Reason"],} \\ \text{categories: ["Yes", "No", "Missing"],} \\ \text{visit: "baseline"} \end{array} \right\}$$

In this example, the *base_entity* represents the primary medical term (“heart attack”). The *associated_entities* indicates related concepts such as “Hospitalization Reason”. The *categories* component specifies potential values such as “Yes”, “No”, “Missing”. The *visit* component indicates the timing context, such as the “baseline”.

These components are treated as separate subqueries (q_1, q_2, q_3) and individually processed to ensure a precise mapping. It is important to note that in a clinical context, different values for each attribute may be present depending on the scenario.

3.2.4. Knowledge retriever

Our retriever module utilizes an ensemble candidate retrieval strategy to enhance precision and contextual relevance. The construction of semantic search spaces involves a dual embedding strategy that serves different retrieval needs, depending on the nature of the concepts.

To generate embeddings, we use two complementary models: SPLADE [49] and SapBERT [26]. SPLADE is used for concept names where an exact match is expected, referred to as “canonical concepts”. These concepts are well-defined terms in controlled vocabularies, which are suitable for keyword-based retrieval. SPLADE efficiently represents these terms in a sparse manner, allowing for highly efficient matching by highlighting relevant keywords and reducing ambiguity.

In contrast, for more nuanced or contextually rich queries, we employ dense representations using SapBERT, a biomedical-specialized pre-trained language model (PLM). The dense embeddings generated by SapBERT are designed to capture subtle variations and relationships between related medical concepts, providing a richer understanding of complex search queries.

Let C denote the set of queries and \mathcal{K} denote the set of concepts from the knowledge base. For each query $Q \in C \cup \mathcal{K}$, the embedding Q_c is generated as follows:

$$Q_c = \text{PLM}(c, \text{syn}(c), \text{info}(c))$$

where $\text{syn}(c)$ represents synonyms of c and $\text{info}(c)$ includes hierarchical information and semantic type. Through this hybrid approach to embedding, we aim to establish a search space that can handle both straightforward and complex retrieval. Candidate generation employs the merging retrieval approach, combining the strength of various retrieval models. The knowledge retriever module retrieves relevant candidates from both the SapBERT and SPLADE models and then passes them to the knowledge filter module.

3.2.5. Knowledge filter

LLMs, despite their impressive capabilities, are susceptible to generating inaccurate or misleading responses when presented with noisy or irrelevant information retrieved during knowledge recovery. Here, noisy information refers to candidates that are irrelevant, semantically misaligned, or only partially relevant to the query. This noise can arise due to issues such as semantic drift (e.g., retrieving “Fear of heart attack” for a query about “heart attack”), ambiguity in query terms, or false positives caused by overgeneration during retrieval. To address this critical challenge, we introduce the Knowledge Filter module, designed to enhance accuracy and precision. Although various filtering strategies exist – such as using LLMs for query-candidate classification or leveraging pre-trained language models (PLMs) with similarity measures – our approach focuses on a dual strategy: metadata-based filtering rules and a similarity threshold-based method to improve performance. The Knowledge Filter module discards candidates that significantly deviate from the query. Formally, this process is represented as follows:

$$\text{Sim}(E(s), E(k)) < \tau$$

where $E(s)$ is the embedding of the source candidate, $E(k)$ is the embedding of the query or context, $\text{Sim}()$ calculates the similarity (e.g., cosine similarity) and τ is the similarity threshold. By filtering out irrelevant or misleading information, the Knowledge Filter reduces the impact of noisy data on an LLM’s output, contributing to more accurate and reliable knowledge-driven responses. The threshold τ can be adjusted to suit different datasets based on the domain-specific concept linking needs of experts.

3.2.6. Knowledge reservoir

The Knowledge Reservoir module aims to reduce an LLM’s inference time during the search and response generation by storing knowledge retrieved in a structured format. It stores label-concept pairs, where the label is the original query and concepts consist of relevant candidates along with their concept codes and OMOP IDs. OMOP IDs are utilized because it is possible for two concept codes from different controlled vocabularies to be identical. For example, the ICD9Proc code for “Other operations in the middle and inner ear” and the OMOP Genomic code for “measurement of the AARS1 gene variant (alanyl-tRNA synthetase 1)” is 20, and the corresponding OMOP IDs are 2000982 and 35956407, respectively. Using OMOP IDs ensures better disambiguation and standardization across vocabularies, providing a consistent and reliable reference for concepts. For the knowledge reservoir, two distinct formats can be used for storage, each serving a specific purpose.

- **Dictionary format:** This format supports efficient direct lookup based on exact matches with the original query label. It is particularly useful for frequent, repetitive queries that require rapid responses, as it allows for direct retrieval without the need for complex searching or reasoning.
- **Triple store format:** This format uses an ontology to store linked concepts as triples (subject, predicate, object), supporting composite CDEs as queries. The triple store structure is advantageous for storing relationships and contextual information, making it possible to represent hierarchical and semantic relationships between entities. This format is useful for handling more intricate queries that require reasoning over the relationships between various data elements.

The reservoir is dynamically updated when new knowledge is retrieved, and its schema can be adjusted as needed. Mathematically, it is represented as a set $K = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{|\mathcal{K}|}\}$, where each k_i is a pair of labels:

$$k_i = (l_i, \{(c_{i1}, o_{i1}), (c_{i2}, o_{i2}), \dots, (c_{in}, o_{in})\})$$

Here, l_i is the label (query), c_{ij} the j th candidate concept and o_{ij} the corresponding OMOP code. Initially, an LLM functions as an automated

Fig. 4. Two-step reranking to select a candidate using a combination of classification and relevance score.

judge, performing zero-shot prompt classification to categorize each concept into *correct*, *partially correct*, and *incorrect* [71]. Concepts classified as *correct* or *partially correct* are then subjected to further validation by domain experts. The experts include clinicians who understand the specific datasets, as well as mapping specialists. This expert review ensures that the final mappings are accurate and clinically interpretable before being preserved in the Knowledge Reservoir for future use.

3.2.7. Two-step reranking

As the next step in our framework, we designed a two-step reranking module, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The prompt design includes the task instruction presented in italics for clarity. It is followed by the context, which comprises the selected candidates followed by the query string. This prompt design aligns with the methodological approach described in [72].

Step 1: Filtered candidates are supplied to an LLM, which leverages its reading comprehension and reasoning capabilities to evaluate and re-rank candidates on a scale from 1 (lowest) to 10 (highest) based on their relevance to the query.

Step 2: An LLM subsequently classifies the top candidates into predefined relevance categories – namely *not relevant*, *partially relevant*, *highly relevant* and *exact match* – assigning scores accordingly: 0–4 for not relevant, between 4 and 7 for partially relevant, 8–9 for highly relevant, and 10 for exact match. These scores facilitate further processing and selection based on the combined outcomes of the previous steps.

To improve the prompt response, we adopt the self-consistency prompting strategy [21], which involves repeatedly prompting the same question to an LLM multiple times. Specifically, we prompt the query with the top candidates altogether as $Q_i, [C_i]$ for $n = 3$ times. We compute a binary confidence score for each response, $B_{i,j} \in [0, 1]$, and derive the average confidence score across prompts. The confidence score for each candidate is determined through a binary transformation

of an LLM's relevance scores. Let $S_{i,j}$ represent the score given to the candidate i in the prompt j . We define a binary score $B_{i,j}$ as follows:

$$B_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } S_{i,j} \geq t \\ 0 & \text{if } S_{i,j} < t \end{cases}$$

The binary scoring method ensures that we consider only candidates who are consistently rated as highly relevant across multiple prompts. The confidence score for each candidate i , denoted as \bar{B}_i , is the average of these binary scores across all n prompts:

$$\bar{B}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n B_{i,j}$$

A candidate is deemed relevant if its average confidence score \bar{B}_i exceeds a predefined threshold τ . The threshold τ is set to $0.85 \times n$, where n is the number of prompts. Thus, a candidate i is considered relevant if $\bar{B}_i > \tau$. Based on our preliminary work (results not shown) to determine the appropriate threshold, we observed that a higher threshold is required in cases where multiple closely aligned candidates are present. This strategy effectively prioritizes the most relevant match among closely aligned candidates while filtering out candidates with lower scores, which are considered irrelevant. This rigorous filtering criterion ensures that only those candidates that consistently achieve high relevance scores in multiple evaluations are selected. We consider a candidate highly relevant if it consistently appears among the top-ranked candidates on multiple prompts. For example, if an LLM identified the same top 3 candidates as highly relevant in each of the prompts, their confidence scores reinforce their relevance. In the case that all candidates are irrelevant, “NA” is returned.

4. Experiment design

This study compares our biomedical concept linking approach against several state-of-the-art models, including SapBERT [26], KRISS

Table 3

Performance comparison of CDE-Mapper variants and baseline models on concept linking tasks. Datasets include NCBI-DC, BC5CDR-D, and HF Studies for linking to controlled vocabularies, as well as MIID for linking MIMIC-IV concepts to the IBKH knowledge base. Results are presented as accuracy at top-1 (acc@1). A dash (–) denotes unavailable results from baseline models.

Models	NCBI-DC	BC5CDR-D	MIID	HF Studies
SapBERT	83.2	86.2	72.9	77.2
KRISS BERT	81	83	50.7	58.9
BioBERT-snomed	80.1	84.8	64.5	39.2
PromptLink	–	–	77.5	–
CDE-Mapper(Llama3.1)	94.4^a	88.2	80.2^a	86.4^a
CDE-Mapper (GPT4o-mini)	93.3	88.6^a	79.2	85.2
CDE-Mapper (GPT4)	88.1	88.3	79.3	83.2

^a Statistically significant improvements are noted compared to both baseline models and other CDE-Mapper variants using different LLMs (T-test, $p < 0.05$).

BERT [28], BioBERT-snomed [54] and an LLM-based approach PromptLink [27]. These baseline models were selected for their demonstrated effectiveness in biomedical tasks and their emphasis on linking individual medical terms to controlled vocabularies. The key differences between our approach and these are that they do not perform retrieval and relevance reranking for composite CDEs.

The datasets presented in Table 1 were used as test entities/variables for concept linking to assess the performance of the proposed approach and the baseline methods. This ensures a consistent and unbiased comparison across all models. Importantly, these datasets represent diverse biomedical contexts, encompassing a mix of controlled vocabulary terms, composite terms, thereby providing a comprehensive benchmark for evaluation.

For query decomposition, we used GPT4, GPT4o-mini (closed source), and Llama3.1 70b (open source) as the black-box LLMs. We used SapBERT [26] and the SPLADE model [49] to generate a semantic search space in the knowledge retrieval module. For similarity, we used the cosine similarity algorithm. For optimal retrieval, the scalar quantization method is employed in the vector database (qdrant v1.10). We selected $k = 10$ as the number of top candidates in the knowledge retrieval module. This decision was based on two considerations. Firstly, $k = 10$ is a commonly accepted baseline and aligns with standard practices in similar tasks, where values in the range of 10–20 are commonly used [26–28,54]. Secondly, this range balances retrieval efficiency and accuracy, including the most relevant candidates without overwhelming the reranking module. For an LLM reranking module, we utilized the same model as used in query decomposition module. To ensure a fair comparison with existing methods, we employed accuracy as a primary metric, as it directly reflects the performance of baseline models on similar tasks, particularly in evaluating the accuracy of the top-ranked predictions. However, since our framework incorporates a reranking module to refine the matched candidate, we also used the Normalized Cumulative Gain Difference (NCGD) metric. NCGD provides a nuanced evaluation of the ranking performance considering the relevance and order of retrieved candidates, making it particularly suitable to assess the effectiveness of our ranking approach in prioritizing clinically relevant matches [73].

5. Results

Our task focuses on automating the concept linking of CDEs using RAG models. The evaluation of various models across datasets, as shown in Table 3, highlights the performance of each approach. Our methodology, leveraging Llama3.1, GPT4o-mini, and GPT4, consistently outperforms the baseline models, demonstrating superior performance in handling diverse types of CDE.

5.1. Performance compared to baselines

Baseline models, including SapBERT, KRISS BERT, and BioBERT-snomed, exhibited high performance on datasets rich in disease mentions, such as NCBI-DC and BC5CDR-D. For example, SapBERT achieved accuracy of 83.2% in NCBI-DC and 86.2% in BC5CDR-D. In comparison, CDE-Mapper using Llama3.1 achieved the highest accuracy of 94.4% in NCBI-DC, outperforming SapBERT by more than 11%. In the BC5CDR-D dataset, GPT4o-mini reached an accuracy of 88.6%, exceeding baseline performance.

In the MIID dataset, Llama3.1 showed a 2.7% improvement over the best-performing baseline. In the HF Studies dataset, which includes composite CDEs, baseline models struggled: SapBERT achieved an accuracy of 77% and KRISS BERT reached 58.9%. In contrast, CDE-Mapper using Llama3.1 demonstrated a significant improvement, achieving an accuracy of 86.4%.

To further evaluate the effectiveness of the CDE-Mapper, we used the NCGD@K metric, which provides additional insight into the model's ranking quality across various datasets. As depicted in Fig. 5, the CDE-Mapper consistently outperformed the baseline models at both NCGD@1 and NCGD@3 levels. Baseline models such as BioBERT-snomed and KRISS BERT showed a noticeable decline in NCG@k values across different datasets, particularly for HF and MIID datasets. This indicates their limitations in capturing domain-specific contextual relationships, which are crucial to handling complex clinical terminologies. For example, in the HF Studies datasets, we observed that BioBERT-snomed struggles to rank the correct concepts high enough, leading to a steeper drop in the NCG@k values.

5.2. Ablation studies and component analysis

To further understand the contributions of individual components within our CDE-Mapper framework, we performed ablation studies across all datasets for various types of CDE. The results, summarized below, illustrate the impact of each component on overall performance.

5.2.1. Performance by CDE type

To evaluate the performance of CDE-Mapper in various types of CDE, we assessed accuracy at (acc@1) compared to baseline models such as SapBERT, KRISS BERT, and BioBERT-snomed, as shown in Table 4.

The analysis highlights the ability of CDE-Mapper to various types of CDE, even when challenged with varying levels of complexity and contextual nuances.

For atomic CDEs, which represent singular and straightforward data elements (e.g., patient sex or age), CDE-Mapper achieved the highest precision of 89.7%, outperforming precision of SapBERT (87.6%) and KRISS BERT (88%). It reflects its strong ability to consistently standardize atomic terms.

Composite CDEs involve complex and interconnected data elements, such as medical conditions with multiple attributes such as severity, onset and related procedures. For these CDEs, CDE-Mapper achieved an accuracy of 80.5%, significantly outperforming KRISS BERT (71.5%) and BioBERT-snomed (65.4%). In the case of dependent CDEs, where normalization depends heavily on the context (e.g., biomarkers such as NT-proBNP, which differ in meaning depending on whether measured in plasma or serum), the CDE-Mapper (Llama3.1, GPT 4o-mini) demonstrated notable performance with an accuracy of 80.5%, significantly exceeding SapBERT accuracy of 66.7%.

Fig. 5. Comparison of NCGD@K for different models across datasets.

Table 4

Accuracy (Acc@1) of CDE-Mapper and baseline models (SapBERT, KRIS5 BERT, BioBERT-snomed) across different CDE types. The CDE-Mapper results are further divided into three variants: Llama3.1, GPT4o-mini, and GPT4. CDEs types include atomic CDEs, composite CDEs which further categories into dependent CDEs. This comparison highlights the performance of each model in linking CDEs to controlled vocabularies, with CDE-Mapper (Llama3.1) consistently achieving the highest accuracy.

CDE types	CDE-Mapper			SapBERT	KRIS5 BERT	BioBERT-snomed
	Llama3.1	GPT4o-mini	GPT4			
Atomic CDEs	89.7	87.6	88	83.8	65.9	50.3
Composite CDEs	80.5	80.5	71.5	65.4	45.1	18
Dependent CDEs	80	80	86.7	66.7	53.3	30

Table 5

Query decomposition on HF studies dataset.

Model	Metric	Attribute extraction	Value extraction
Llama3.1	Precision	0.63	0.83
	Recall	1.00	0.86
	F1	0.78	0.84
GPT4	Precision	0.63	0.85
	Recall	1.00	0.84
	F1	0.78	0.85
GPT4o-mini	Precision	0.63	0.83
	Recall	1.00	0.84
	F1	0.78	0.82

5.2.2. Performance of query decomposition

We evaluated the query decomposition module using the dataset from the HF Studies, where the definitions of the variables and associated attributes served as input. The ground truth was manually curated with the help of two domain experts. The evaluation of true positive was conducted using two key metrics:

- **Exact word-match:** Measures how accurately the model extracted attributes (e.g., base entity, domain, associated entities, categories, and unit).

- **Fuzzy word-match:** Measures how accurately the model extracted values for each relationship, allowing minor variations.
- **Base entity:** Indicates whether the mention was correctly identified as a base entity, grouped with a valid base entity, or placed in the correct field within the corresponding base entity group (as a JSON object)

The results of the query decomposition are summarized in Table 5. All models demonstrated identical precision in attribute extraction, each achieving a precision of 0.63 and a perfect recall of 1.00, resulting in an F1 score of 0.78. In value extraction, the models maintained similar precision scores, ranging from 0.83 to 0.85. However, slight variations in recall led to differences in F1 scores. GPT4 achieved the highest F1 score of 0.85 due to its superior precision (0.85) and competitive recall (0.84), while Llama3.1 achieved an F1 score of 0.84 with a precision of 0.83 and a recall of 0.86. GPT4o-mini recorded a slightly lower F1 score of 0.82, maintaining a precision of 0.83 and a recall of 0.84. These findings indicate that, while precision was consistent across all models, minor differences in recall contributed to variations in their overall performance in value extraction.

5.2.3. Impact of Knowledge Filtering (KF)

The introduction of knowledge filtering, combined with a merger retriever that integrates dense and sparse retrieval mechanisms, resulted

Table 6
Acc@k retrieval performance with different retriever configurations across datasets.

Datasets	Retriever	Acc@1	Acc@3	Acc@5	Acc@10
MIID	Ensemble (label only)	70.3	86.2	89.4	90.7
	Ensemble+KF (label only)	71.5	88.1	90	90.8
	Ensemble (context-aware)	73.3	86.2	89.4	91
	Ensemble+KF (context-aware)	75.3	88	90	92.8
NCBI-DC	Ensemble (label only)	91.5	94.6	95.2	95.2
	Ensemble+KF (label only)	88.7	91.8	92.4	92.6
	Ensemble (context-aware)	92.7	95.8	96.3	96.6
	Ensemble+KF (context-aware)	92.7	95.8	96.3	96.6
BC5CDR-D	Ensemble (label only)	90.5	94	95.2	95.9
	Ensemble+KF (label only)	90.5	94	95.2	95.9
	Ensemble (context-aware)	90.5	94.3	95.2	95.9
	Ensemble+KF (context-aware)	90.5	93.6	95	95.9
HF Studies	Ensemble (label only)	76.9	91.4	94.5	95.8
	Ensemble+KF (label only)	77.4	91.6	94.5	95.8
	Ensemble (context-aware)	78.1	91.6	94.5	95.8
	Ensemble+KF (context-aware)	77.8	91.4	94.7	96

in significant improvements in retrieval accuracy. Table 6 presents the retrieval performance with accuracy at k (acc@k) of various retrieval configurations in selected datasets. The results indicate that the incorporation of KF consistently improved the retrieval performance in most datasets. Specifically, transitioning from **Ensemble (label only)** to **Ensemble+KF (label only)** yields modest improvements in certain datasets such as MIID, with acc@1 increasing from 70.3% to 71.5%. Additionally, context-aware configurations showed further benefit, demonstrating higher retrieval accuracies compared to the non-KF counterparts. The **Ensemble+KF (context-aware)** configuration consistently outperforms other MIID configurations, achieving an acc@1 of 75.3%, highlighting the synergistic benefits of combining ensemble methods with knowledge filtering and context-awareness. For the HF Studies dataset, **Ensemble+KF (context-aware)** demonstrated slight improvements in acc@1, increasing from 76% to 77.8%.

5.2.4. Role of two-step reranking

To evaluate the effectiveness of the stepwise reranking mechanism within our framework, we performed additional experiments on selected datasets using different models. Specifically, we evaluated the performance implications of both steps in our two-step reranking process. The first step involves reranking candidates using a relevance score ranging from 1 to 10, while the second step classifies these reranked candidates into predefined relevance categories based on their scores.

The reranking performance of three models—Llama3.1, GPT4o-mini, and GPT4 across various datasets at acc@[1,3] is shown in Table 7. The results demonstrate that reranking consistently improves retrieval performance in all datasets and models. For example, in the HF Studies dataset, Llama3.1 improved from 85.4% at step 1 to 86.2% at step 2, while GPT4o-mini showed an improvement from 84.5% to 86.4%. Similarly, GPT4 improved from 81.4% at step 1 to 83.2% at step 2, indicating that the reranking step effectively enhances the retrieved results.

In particular, the NCBI-DC dataset showed the highest performance gains, with Llama3.1 reaching 94.4% in step 2. In contrast, the MIID dataset showed modest improvements across all models, likely due to the inherent complexity and variability of the concepts involved. The BC5CDR-D dataset maintained stable performance, with GPT4o-mini reaching the highest accuracy of 88.6%.

5.3. Case study

To further assess the performance of our proposed CDE-Mapper framework, we conducted a case study using various CDEs, as shown in Table 8. This analysis focuses on instances where baseline models

Table 7
Two-step reranking performance at Acc@1 and Acc@3 for different LLMs across datasets.

Models	HF Studies	NCBI-DC	MIID	BC5CDR-D
Llama3.1 (Step 1)	85.4, 89.0	94.2, 96.4	79.9, 89.3	87.1, 91.9
Llama3.1 (Step 2)	86.4, 92.3	94.4, 96.6	80.2, 89.8	88.1, 92.8
GPT4o-mini (Step 1)	84.5, 93.2	92.8, 96.4	70.8, 75.4	87.9, 93.1
GPT4o-mini (Step 2)	85.2, 93.4	93.3, 96.9	79.2, 88.1	88.6, 90.3
GPT4 (Step 1)	81.4, 90.2	87.5, 92.4	77.5, 86.6	87.3, 92.6
GPT4 (Step 2)	83.2, 91.7	88.1, 92.4	79.3, 86.8	88.3, 92.6

such as SapBERT, KRISS BERT, and BioBERT-snomed either struggled or succeeded in comparison to CDE-Mapper, particularly in handling complex CDEs, rare conditions and ambiguous terminologies.

In this case study, we evaluated three scenarios including (1) concepts evaluated by both ground truth labels and two clinicians; (2) concepts evaluated by clinicians due to missing ground truth labels; (3) cases that require further context. Overall, the CDE-Mapper model showed consistently higher performance in all three cases compared to baseline. In Case II, the unit “pmol/L” (picomole per liter) is a precise measurement used in laboratory results. SapBERT and KRISS BERT incorrectly mapped this to “micromole per liter”, which represents a different magnitude and could lead to significant clinical misinterpretations. BioBERT-snomed mapped it to “picogram per milliliter”, also an incorrect unit. In contrast, CDE-Mapper accurately linked it to “picomole per liter”, matching the ground truth and demonstrating its ability to handle specific measurement units accurately.

In scenarios without ground truth, such as Case XI involves the composite CDE “heart rate measured in the recumbent position”, where the positional context is clinically significant. SapBERT mapped this to “resting heart rate” and KRISS BERT to “pulse rate measured by palpation”, both of which failed to capture the importance of the recumbent position. BioBERT-snomed provided “heart rate unspecified time mean by the pedometer”, which is unrelated. CDE-Mapper successfully mapped it to joint concepts “heart rate | recumbent body position”, effectively capturing the positional context necessary for an accurate clinical evaluation.

Another challenging example is Case XII, which involves “mild to moderate asthma exacerbations”. This term requires an accurate standardization of both the condition and its severity. SapBERT mapped it to “exacerbation of mild persistent asthma”, capturing the “mild” aspect but potentially missing the “moderate” severity. KRISS BERT mapped it to “moderate persistent asthma”, focusing on the “moderate” aspect. BioBERT-snomed also mapped it to “exacerbation of mild persistent asthma”. CDE-Mapper mapped it to two concepts “acute asthma|mild to moderate”, encompassing both severity levels and aligning with clinical interpretations. It shows the CDE-Mapper’s capability to handle composite terms involving nuanced severity gradations more effectively than the baseline models.

In Case XIV, the term “geniculate herpes zoster” refers to a specific viral infection affecting the facial nerve, commonly known as herpes zoster oticus or Ramsay Hunt Syndrome Type II. SapBERT correctly mapped it to “herpes zoster oticus”, aligning both with ground truth and clinical acceptance. KRISS BERT incorrectly assigned it to “herpes simplex keratitis”, which is a different condition affecting the eye. BioBERT-snomed mapped it to a synonym term “herpes zoster auricularis”, a clinically correct interpretation. CDE-Mapper mapped it to “Ramsay Hunt Syndrome Type II”, another synonym, while clinically appropriate, is not the correct term according to the ground truth. This indicates that CDE-Mapper is able to find clinically relevant terms where ground truth may or may not include them, which is crucial for clinical accuracy and interoperability. However, in Case VII, involving “nonspecific T wave abnormality, improved in on eeg”, none of the models, including CDE-Mapper, produced the correct candidate. These instances highlight areas where CDE-Mapper excels and areas that require further refinement.

Table 8
Model predictions with clinician and ground truth justifications.

ID	Use-Case	SapBERT	KRISS BERT	BioBERT-snomed	CDE-Mapper (Llama3.1)
I	Hypercholesterolemia as a comorbid condition	Secondary hypercholesterolemia	Hypercholesterolemia		
II	pmol/L	Micromole per liter	Micromole per liter	Picogram per milliliter	Picomole per liter
III	N-terminal pro b-type natriuretic peptide in blood	Plasma n-terminal pro b-type natriuretic peptide concentration measurement	n-terminal pro b-type natriuretic peptide mass concentration in serum	Natriuretic peptide.b prohormone n-terminal [mass/volume] in blood by immunoassay	Natriuretic peptide.b prohormone n-terminal substance concentration moment in time blood, serum or plasma
IV	Heart failure worsening	Exacerbation of heart failure			
V	Diuretics dose expressed in an amount equivalent to Furosemide	Furosemide dose drug doses			
VI	o.i.d	o.d. unit	o.d. unit	1/day	
VII	Nonspecific t wave abnormality, improved in on ecg	Nonspecific st-t abnormality on electrocardiogram	Nonspecific st-t abnormality on electrocardiogram	Nonspecific st-t abnormality on electrocardiogram	Nonspecific st-t abnormality on electrocardiogram
VIII	Date of baseline visit	Birth date	Date of visit	Date of visit	Date of first visit
IX	mmhg	Millimeter	hg	Liter per minute	Millimeter mercury column
X	Nyha class in half increments	New york heart association classification class			
XI	Heart rate measured in recumbent position	Resting heart rate	Pulse rate measured by palpation	Heart rate unspecified time mean by pedometer	Heart rate recumbent body position
XII	Mild to moderate asthma exacerbation	Exacerbation of mild persistent asthma	Moderate persistent asthma	Exacerbation of mild persistent asthma	Acute asthma mild to moderate
XIII	Patient followed up 3 days after discharge	Post hospital discharge followed up within 3 days			
XIV	Geniculate herpes zoster	Herpes zoster oticus			
XV	Man	Humanist	Bisexual	Male	
XVI	NYHA class: No limitation of physical activity	New york heart association classification - class i			
XVII	Vena cava inferior max diameter on echocardiography	Diameter inferior vena cava cardiac ultrasound			

 indicates the ground truth prediction.

 indicates predictions considered correct by clinicians.

6. Discussion

The empirical results demonstrate the efficacy of the CDE-Mapper framework in comparison to established baseline models. Specifically, CDE-Mapper, leveraging Llama3.1 and GPT4o-mini, consistently outperforms these baselines across multiple datasets. This superior performance suggests that the integration of RAG techniques, knowledge filtering, and a two-step reranking process significantly enhances accuracy of concept linking.

In query decomposition, all models demonstrated comparable performance in attribute extraction, achieving perfect recall but moderate precision. For value extraction, both Llama3.1 and GPT4 achieved high recall, with GPT4 exhibiting the highest precision. Despite these strengths, all models showed similar weaknesses, particularly in normalizing context-dependent measurements, units, abbreviations, and

acronyms. These observations highlight the need for further improvements in handling nuanced clinical data elements that require domain-specific contextual understanding.

Incorporation of knowledge filtering significantly improved the performance in the MIID dataset, with the Ensemble+KF (context-aware) configuration achieving an acc@1 of 75.3%. In the BC5CDR-D dataset, no significant improvements were observed, with Ensemble+KF (context-aware) achieving performance similar to other configurations. This limited enhancement is likely due to the scarcity of contextual information available for many concepts in the dataset where only 6530 out of 73,412 concepts had hierarchical information (parent terms), and 7097 had synonyms. The lack of sufficient synonyms and hierarchical data constrained the effectiveness of knowledge filtering and context-aware methods, underscoring the reliance of our approach on the availability of comprehensive and faceted attributes.

Nevertheless, our findings demonstrate that knowledge filtering generally improves retrieval precision and relevance, particularly when rich semantic information is present.

The two-step reranking mechanism also proved effective in refining retrieval results. Models such as Llama3.1, GPT4o-mini, and GPT4 showed measurable performance gains from Step 1 to Step 2 across several datasets. The NCBI-DC dataset benefited most from reranking, while more complex datasets like MIID showed modest gains, likely due to variability in entity labels and definitions. In the BC5CDR-D dataset, minimal improvements were observed with reranking and knowledge filtering—again reflecting the dependency on richer semantic structures. Additionally, reranking did not consistently outperform acc@k scores from knowledge filtering when $k \in [5, 10]$, suggesting that retrieval with broader candidate selection may sometimes be more effective than strict reranking refinement.

Each component contributes incrementally to the overall accuracy, highlighting the importance of a multifaceted approach in the standardization of composite CDEs. These results validate the benefit of combining semantic retrieval, knowledge filtering, and reranking processes to achieve superior concept linking. Within the Knowledge Reservoir, the dual-layer validation process – combining automated LLM assessment with expert review – prevents the propagation of erroneous or sub-optimal mappings. Only concepts that pass both validation stages are retained, thereby ensuring the integrity and reliability of the knowledge base for downstream applications.

Overall, the integration of context-sensitive mechanisms that leverage semantic information from diverse controlled vocabularies significantly enhances both precision and interpretability. Taken together, the discussion of these findings underscores a clear pathway toward improved concept linking through a holistic and modular design.

6.1. Limitations

This study demonstrates the significant potential of leveraging RAG models to standardize various types of CDE using controlled vocabularies, overcoming the challenges faced by existing methods. However, several limitations highlight areas for future improvement.

One major limitation lies in the variability of the model's output based on the quality of contextual examples provided to an LLM. Although the default template of linking rules is robust, deviations in template structure or contextual examples can lead to inconsistently linked concepts. This highlights the dependency on domain expertise to create high-quality prompts and examples. Future research should explore automated techniques for generating effective prompts, such as reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) or low-resource fine-tuning methods.

Performance gains through reranking were not always highly significant, suggesting the need to refine the reranking mechanism or explore alternative methods to ensure the retrieval of highly relevant results. Furthermore, some edge cases, particularly those involving nuanced contextual linking (e.g., “geniculate herpes zoster”, “nonspecific T wave abnormality, improved on the ECG”), highlight the limitations of RAG models. Such cases emphasize the need for continuous model refinement and the incorporation of human oversight, especially in high-stakes clinical applications.

Another limitation is the framework's reliance on comprehensive and high-quality controlled vocabularies. The success of knowledge-filtering and-retrieval components depends on the availability of rich synonyms and semantic relationships in the knowledge base. Sparse or incomplete vocabularies may limit the framework's efficacy, as observed in datasets like BC5CDR-D, where insufficient synonyms constrained performance improvements. Further research could investigate the dynamic integration of multiple knowledge sources or the addition of existing vocabularies with crowd-sourced data.

Finally, the computational cost and inference speed of LLMs remain significant challenges. Although open source models such as Llama3.1

offer a cost-effective alternative to proprietary models such as GPT4, they still require substantial computational resources for local deployment. Techniques such as model quantization, distillation, and adaptive compression could reduce the computational footprint while maintaining accuracy. Furthermore, developing domain-specific LLMs with efficient architectures could address the high-resource requirements for inference.

7. Conclusions

This study introduces CDE-Mapper, a framework that uses the RAG technique to automate the linking of clinical data elements to controlled vocabularies. By integrating modular components—including query decomposition, ensemble retrieval, knowledge filtering, and two-step reranking. Our approach demonstrates significant advancements over baseline models, particularly in handling complex and composite CDEs. Our evaluation across diverse datasets highlights the framework's scalability and effectiveness, achieving state-of-the-art accuracy while maintaining cost-efficiency through the use of open-source models such as Llama3.1. These advancements are critical for enhancing data interoperability, enabling seamless integration of heterogeneous datasets, and supporting advanced clinical decision-making.

Future research should focus on addressing identified limitations, such as optimizing computational efficiency, expanding vocabulary coverage, and refining contextual understanding. By incorporating adaptive learning techniques and domain-specific enhancements, the framework can further improve its robustness and applicability to diverse healthcare contexts. Ultimately, this work highlights the transformative potential of combining RAG models with controlled vocabularies, paving the way for more accurate, scalable, and efficient data standardization solutions in the era of digital health.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Komal Gilani: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Marlo Verket:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Christof Peters:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Michel Dumontier:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Hans-Peter Brunner-La Rocca:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Visara Urovi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethical approval for CHECK-HF was provided by the Ethical Committee of the Maastricht University Medical Center, the Netherlands. Ethical approval for TIME-CHF was provided by the Ethical Committee of Both Basel (EKBB), Switzerland.

Code availability

The code used in this study is available at https://github.com/komi786/cde_mapper.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. Algorithm

Algorithm 1 Clinical Terms Linking Process

Require: Dictionary of source terms D , linking rules template M
Ensure: All sub-terms in D are mapped to standard terminologies according to M

```

1: Initialize list  $N \leftarrow []$  ▷ List to store linked concepts for each query
2: for each query  $q \in D$  do
3:    $q \leftarrow \text{ValidateInput}(q)$  ▷ Ensure  $q$  conforms to expected format
4:    $result \leftarrow \text{DecomposeQuery}(q)$  ▷ Decompose query into
   components  $q_i$ 
5:   if  $result \neq \emptyset$  then
6:     Initialize  $candidate\_result \leftarrow \{\}$  ▷ Dictionary to store
     candidates for  $q$ 
7:     for each component  $q_i$  in  $result$  do
8:        $kr\_match \leftarrow \text{CheckInKR}(q_i)$  ▷ Check if candidates exists
       in Knowledge Reservoir
9:       if  $kr\_match \neq \emptyset$  then
10:         $candidate\_result[q_i] \leftarrow kr\_match$  ▷ Use existing
        candidates
11:       else
12:         $candidates \leftarrow \text{MergeRetrievers}(q_i)$  ▷ Retrieve
        potential candidates
13:         $candidates \leftarrow \text{KGFilter}(candidates, q_i, rules)$  ▷ Filter
        candidates based on expert rules and semantic relevance
14:        if  $candidates \neq \emptyset$  then
15:           $match \leftarrow \text{FindExactMatch}(candidates, q_i)$ 
16:          if  $match \neq \emptyset$  then
17:             $candidate\_result[q_i] \leftarrow match$  ▷ Add to
            result for  $q$ 
18:          else
19:             $scores \leftarrow \text{MultistepLLMScore}(candidates)$  ▷
            Re-rank candidates based on LLM scoring
20:             $selected\_candidate \leftarrow \text{SelectTopCandidate}(scores)$ 
            ▷ Select top candidate
21:             $candidate\_result[q_i] \leftarrow selected\_candidate$ 
22:          end if
23:        else
24:           $candidate\_result[q_i] \leftarrow \text{"NA"}$  ▷ No suitable
          candidates found
25:        end if
26:         $\text{AddInKR}(q_i, candidate\_result[q_i])$  ▷ Add new
        candidate to Knowledge Reservoir
27:      end if
28:    end for
29:     $N \leftarrow N \cup \{candidate\_result\}$  ▷ Add candidate result for  $q$ 
    to  $N$ 
30:  else
31:     $N \leftarrow N \cup \{\text{"NA"}\}$  ▷ Add "NA" if decomposition fails
32:  end if
33: end for
return  $N$ 

```

References

- [1] L.R. Kalankesh, E. Monaghesh, Utilization of EHRs for clinical trials: a systematic review, *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 24 (1) (2024) 70, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12874-024-02170-2>.
- [2] E. Hutchings, M.W. Loomes, P. Butow, F. Boyle, A systematic literature review of researchers' and healthcare professionals' attitudes towards the secondary use and sharing of health administrative and clinical trial data, *Syst. Rev.* 9 (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01485-5>.
- [3] A.E. Whitlock, G. Leroy, F.M. Donovan, J.N. Galgiani, ICD codes are insufficient to create datasets for machine learning: An evaluation using all of us data for coccidioidomycosis and myocardial infarction, in: 2024 IEEE 12th International Conference on Healthcare Informatics, ICHI, IEEE, 2024, pp. 129–134, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICHI61247.2024.00024>.
- [4] F. Hardy, J. Heyl, K. Tucker, A. Hopper, M.J. Marchã, T.W.R. Briggs, J. Yates, J. Day, A. Wheeler, S. Eve-Jones, W.K. Gray, Data consistency in the english hospital episodes statistics database, *BMJ Heal. Care Inf.* 29 (1) (2022) e100633, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjhci-2022-100633>.
- [5] E. French, B.T. McInnes, An overview of biomedical entity linking throughout the years, *J. Biomed. Inf.* 137 (2023) 104252.
- [6] W. Shen, Y. Li, Y. Liu, J. Han, J. Wang, X. Yuan, Entity linking meets deep learning: Techniques and solutions, *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.* 35 (2021) 2556–2578, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2021.3117715>.
- [7] Z.A. Guven, A. Lamurias, Multilingual bi-encoder models for biomedical entity linking, *Expert Syst.* 40 (2023) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/exsy.13388>.
- [8] V. Cutrona, F. Bianchi, E. Jiménez-Ruiz, M. Palmonari, Tough tables: Carefully evaluating entity linking for tabular data, in: *International Semantic Web Conference*, Springer, 2020, pp. 328–343.
- [9] M. Kulyabin, G. Sokolov, A. Galaïda, A. Maier, T. Arias-Vergara, Snobert: A benchmark for clinical notes entity linking in the SNOMED ct clinical terminology, 2024, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.16115>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [10] E.H. Houssein, R.E. Mohamed, A.A. Ali, Machine learning techniques for biomedical natural language processing: A comprehensive review, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 140628–140653, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3119621>.
- [11] D. Loureiro, A.M. Jorge, Medlinker: Medical entity linking with neural representations and dictionary matching, in: *Advances in Information Retrieval: 42nd European Conference on IR Research, ECIR 2020, Lisbon, Portugal, April 14–17, 2020, Proceedings, Part II*, in: *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 12036, 2020, pp. 230–237, http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-45442-5_29.
- [12] N. Perera, M. Dehmer, F. Emmert-Streib, Named entity recognition and relation detection for biomedical information extraction, *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* 8 (2020) 673, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2020.00673>.
- [13] T. Abdullahi, L. Mercurio, R. Singh, C. Eickhoff, Retrieval-based diagnostic decision support: Mixed methods study, *JMIR Med. Inf.* 12 (2024) e50209, <http://dx.doi.org/10.2196/50209>.
- [14] L. Soldaini, N. Goharian, QuickUMLS: A fast, unsupervised approach for medical concept extraction, in: *Proceedings of the SIGIR 2016 Workshop on Medical Information Retrieval (MedIR)*, 2016, pp. 1–4.
- [15] LHNBCB, Lhncbc/metamaplite: A near real-time named-entity recognizer, 2017, <https://github.com/lhncbc/metamaplite>. (Accessed 18 July 2024).
- [16] G.K. Savova, J.J. Masanz, P.V. Ogren, J. Zheng, S. Sohn, K.C. Kipper-Schuler, C.G. Chute, Mayo clinical text analysis and knowledge extraction system (ctakes): Architecture, component evaluation and applications, *J. Am. Med. Inf. Assoc.* 17 (5) (2010) 507–513, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/jamia.2009.001560>.
- [17] W.X. Zhao, K. Zhou, J. Li, T. Tang, X. Wang, Y. Hou, Y. Min, B. Zhang, J. Zhang, Z. Dong, et al., A survey of large language models, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.18223>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [18] H. Naveed, A.U. Khan, S. Qiu, M. Saqib, S. Anwar, M. Usman, N. Akhtar, N. Barnes, A. Mian, A comprehensive overview of large language models, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.06435>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [19] A.J. Thirunavukarasu, D.S.J. Ting, K. Elangovan, L. Gutierrez, T.F. Tan, D.S.W. Ting, Large language models in medicine, *Nat. Med.* 29 (8) (2023) 1930–1940.
- [20] Y. Chang, X. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Wu, L. Yang, K. Zhu, H. Chen, X. Yi, C. Wang, Y. Wang, W. Ye, Y. Zhang, Y. Chang, P.S. Yu, Q. Yang, X. Xie, A survey on evaluation of large language models, *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.* 15 (3) (2024) 39, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3641289>.
- [21] P. Lewis, E. Perez, A. Piktus, F. Petroni, V. Karpukhin, N. Goyal, H. Küttler, M. Lewis, W. Yih, T. Rocktäschel, S. Riedel, D. Kiela, Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks, in: *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2020)*, NIPS '20, 2020, p. 793.
- [22] S. Thapa, S. Adhikari, ChatGPT, bard, and large language models for biomedical research: Opportunities and pitfalls, *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 51 (12) (2023) 2647–2651, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10439-023-03284-0>.

- [23] J.H. Caufield, H. Hegde, V. Emonet, N.L. Harris, M.P. Joachimiak, N. Matentzoglou, H. Kim, S. Moxon, J.T. Reese, M.A. Haendel, P.N. Robinson, C.J. Mungall, Structured prompt interrogation and recursive extraction of semantics (SPIRES): A method for populating knowledge bases using zero-shot learning, *Bioinform.* 40 (3) (2024) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btae104>.
- [24] L. Huang, W. Yu, W. Ma, W. Zhong, Z. Feng, H. Wang, Q. Chen, W. Peng, X. Feng, B. Qin, T. Liu, A survey on hallucination in large language models: Principles, taxonomy, challenges, and open questions, *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.* 43 (2) (2025) 42, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3703155>.
- [25] Y. Gao, Y. Xiong, X. Gao, K. Jia, J. Pan, Y. Bi, Y. Dai, J. Sun, M. Wang, H. Wang, Retrieval-augmented generation for large language models: A survey, 2024, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.10997>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [26] F. Liu, E. Shareghi, Z. Meng, M. Basaldella, N. Collier, Self-alignment pretraining for biomedical entity representations, in: Proceedings of the 2021 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, 2021, pp. 4228–4238, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.naacl-main.334>.
- [27] Y. Xie, J. Lu, J. Ho, F. Nahab, X. Hu, C. Yang, PromptLink: Leveraging large language models for cross-source biomedical concept linking, in: Proceedings of the 47th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, SIGIR 2024, 2024, pp. 2589–2593, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3626772.3657904>.
- [28] S. Zhang, H. Cheng, S. Vashishth, C. Wong, J. Xiao, X. Liu, T. Naumann, J. Gao, H. Poon, Knowledge-rich self-supervision for biomedical entity linking, 2021, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.07887>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [29] J. Sheehan, S. Hirschfeld, E. Foster, U. Ghitza, K. Goetz, J. Karpinski, L. Lang, R.P. Moser, J. Odenkirchen, D. Reeves, Y. Rubinstein, E. Werner, M. Huerta, Improving the value of clinical research through the use of common data elements, *Clin. Trials* 13 (6) (2016) 671–676, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1740774516653238>.
- [30] H. Le Sueur, I.N. Bruce, N. Geifman, Masterplans Consortium, The challenges in data integration: heterogeneity and complexity in clinical trials and patient registries of systemic lupus erythematosus, *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 20 (1) (2020) 164, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01057-0>.
- [31] H.H. Kim, Y.R. Park, S. Lee, J.H. Kim, Composite CDE: Modeling composite relationships between common data elements for representing complex clinical data, *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.* 20 (2020) 147, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12911-020-01168-0>.
- [32] R. Platt, J.S. Brown, M. Robb, M. McClellan, R. Ball, M.D. Nguyen, R.E. Sherman, The FDA sentinel initiative—An evolving national resource, *N. Engl. J. Med.* 379 (22) (2018) 2091–2093, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp1809643>.
- [33] J.G. Klann, M.A.H. Joss, K. Embree, S.N. Murphy, Data model harmonization for the all of us research program: Transforming i2b2 data into the OMOP common data model, *PLoS One* 14 (2) (2019) e0212463, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0212463>.
- [34] P.E. Stang, P.B. Ryan, J.A. Racoosin, J.M. Overhage, A.G. Hartzema, C. Reich, E. Welebob, T. Scarnecchia, J. Woodcock, Advancing the science for active surveillance: rationale and design for the observational medical outcomes partnership, *Ann. Intern. Med.* 153 (9) (2010) 600–606, <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-153-9-201011020-00010>.
- [35] M. Lehne, J. Sass, A. Essenwanger, J. Schepers, S. Thun, Why digital medicine depends on interoperability, *Npj Digit. Med.* 2 (2019) 79, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0158-1>.
- [36] J.M. Reips, M.J. Schuemie, M.A. Suchard, P.B. Ryan, P.R. Rijnbeek, Design and implementation of a standardized framework to generate and evaluate patient-level prediction models using observational healthcare data, *J. Am. Med. Assoc.* 25 (8) (2018) 969–975, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocy032>.
- [37] V. Papez, M. Moinat, S. Payralbe, F.W. Asselbergs, R.T. Lumbers, H. Hemingway, R. Dobson, S. Denaxas, Transforming and evaluating electronic health record disease phenotyping algorithms using the OMOP common data model: A case study in heart failure, *JAMIA Open* 4 (3) (2021) ooab001, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooab001>.
- [38] N. Ahmadi, M. Zoch, O. Guengoeze, C. Facchinello, A. Mondorf, K. Stratmann, K. Musleh, H.P. Erasmus, J. Tchertov, R. Gebler, et al., How to customize common data models for rare diseases: an OMOP-based implementation and lessons learned, *Orphanet J. Rare Dis.* 19 (1) (2024) 298, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13023-024-03312-9>.
- [39] P. Biedermann, R. Ong, A. Davydog, A. Orlova, P. Solovyev, H. Sun, G. Wetherill, M. Brand, E.-M. Didden, Standardizing registry data to the OMOP Common Data Model: Experience from three pulmonary hypertension databases, *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 21 (2021) 238, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01434-3>.
- [40] G. Izacard, P. Lewis, M. Lomeli, L. Hosseini, F. Petroni, T. Schick, J. Dwivedi-Yu, A. Joulin, S. Riedel, E. Grave, Atlas: Few-shot learning with retrieval augmented language models, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 24 (1) (2023) 251.
- [41] O. Rubin, J. Herzig, J. Berant, Learning to retrieve prompts for in-context learning, in: Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, NAACL-HLT 2022, 2022, pp. 2655–2671, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.191>.
- [42] Q. Dong, L. Li, D. Dai, C. Zheng, J. Ma, R. Li, H. Xia, J. Xu, Z. Wu, B. Chang, X. Sun, L. Li, Z. Sui, A survey on in-context learning, in: Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, EMNLP 2024, 2024, pp. 1107–1128, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.emnlp-main.64>.
- [43] Qingxiu Dong, Lei Li, Damai Dai, Ce Zheng, Jingyuan Ma, Rui Li, Heming Xia, Jingjing Xu, Zhiyong Wu, Tianyu Liu, et al., A survey on in-context learning, 2022, arXiv preprint [arXiv:2301.00234](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.00234).
- [44] J. Liu, D. Shen, Y. Zhang, B. Dolan, L. Carin, W. Chen, What makes good in-context examples for GPT-3? in: Proceedings of Deep Learning Inside Out (DeeLIO 2022): The 3rd Workshop on Knowledge Extraction and Integration for Deep Learning Architectures, 2022, pp. 100–114, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.deeLIO-1.10>.
- [45] W. Shi, J. Michael, S. Gururangan, L. Zettlemoyer, kNN-prompt: Nearest neighbor zero-shot inference, 2022, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.13792>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [46] J. Chen, H. Lin, X. Han, L. Sun, Benchmarking large language models in retrieval-augmented generation, in: Proceedings of the Thirty-Eighth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI 2024, 2024, p. 1980, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v38i16.29728>.
- [47] T. Wolf, L. Debut, V. Sanh, J. Chaumond, C. Delangue, A. Moi, P. Cistac, T. Rault, R. Louf, M. Funtowicz, J. Davison, S. Shleifer, P. von Platen, C. Ma, Y. Jernite, J. Plu, C. Xu, T. Le Scao, S. Gugger, M. Drame, Q. Lhoest, A.M. Rush, Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing, in: Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations, EMNLP-Demos 2020, 2020, pp. 38–45, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6>.
- [48] D. Chandrasekaran, V. Mago, Evolution of semantic similarity—a survey, *ACM Comput. Surv.* 54 (2) (2021) 41, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3440755>.
- [49] T. Formal, B. Piwowarski, S. Clinchant, SPLADE: Sparse lexical and expansion model for first stage ranking, in: Proceedings of the 44th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, SIGIR '21, 2021, pp. 2288–2292, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3404835.3463098>.
- [50] B. Song, F. Li, Y. Liu, X. Zeng, Deep learning methods for biomedical named entity recognition: A survey and qualitative comparison, *Brief. Bioinform.* 22 (6) (2021) bbab282, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbab282>.
- [51] M. Sung, H. Jeon, J. Lee, J. Kang, Biomedical entity representations with synonym marginalization, 2020, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.00239>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [52] C. Yan, Y. Zhang, K. Liu, J. Zhao, Y. Shi, S. Liu, Biomedical concept normalization by leveraging hypernyms, in: Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, EMNLP 2021, 2021, pp. 3512–3517, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.emnlp-main.284>.
- [53] J.G. Zheng, D. Howson, B. Zhang, J. Hahn, D. McGuinness, J. Hendler, H. Ji, Entity linking for biomedical literature, *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.* 15 (Suppl 1) (2015) S4, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1472-6947-15-S1-S4>.
- [54] J. Lee, W. Yoon, S. Kim, D. Kim, S. Kim, C.H. So, J. Kang, BioBERT: a pre-trained biomedical language representation model for biomedical text mining, *Bioinform.* 36 (4) (2020) 1234–1240, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz682>.
- [55] T. Zhu, Y. Qin, Q. Chen, B. Hu, Y. Xiang, Enhancing entity representations with prompt learning for biomedical entity linking, in: Proceedings of the 31st International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI-22, 2022, pp. 4036–4042, <http://dx.doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2022/560>.
- [56] T. Zhu, Y. Qin, M. Feng, Q. Chen, B. Hu, Y. Xiang, Biopro: Context-infused prompt learning for biomedical entity linking, *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* 32 (2023) 374–385.
- [57] L. Wang, Q. Wang, H. Bai, C. Liu, W. Liu, Y. Zhang, L. Jiang, H. Xu, K. Wang, Y. Zhou, EHR2Vec: Representation learning of medical concepts from temporal patterns of clinical notes based on self-attention mechanism, *Front. Genet.* 11 (2020) 630, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2020.0630>.
- [58] J. Achiam, S. Adler, S. Agarwal, L. Ahmad, I. Akkaya, F.L. Aleman, D. Almeida, J. Altschmidt, S. Altman, S. Anadkat, et al., GPT-4 technical report, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.08774>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [59] H. Touvron, T. Lavril, G. Izacard, Y. Martinet, M.-A. Lachaux, T. Lacroix, B. Rozière, N. Goyal, E. Hambro, F. Azhar, et al., Llama: Open and efficient foundation language models, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.13971>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [60] K. Soman, P.W. Rose, J.H. Morris, R.E. Akbas, B. Smith, B. Peetoom, C. Villouta-Reyes, G. Ceroni, Y. Shi, A. Rizk-Jackson, S. Israni, C.A. Nelson, S. Huang, S.E. Baranzini, Biomedical knowledge graph-optimized prompt generation for large language models, *Bioinform.* 40 (9) (2024) btae560, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btae560>.
- [61] R.C. Fernandez, A.J. Elmore, M.J. Franklin, S. Krishnan, C. Tan, How large language models will disrupt data management, *Proc. VLDB Endow.* 16 (11) (2023) 3302–3309, <http://dx.doi.org/10.14778/3611479.3611527>.
- [62] R. Peeters, A. Steiner, C. Bizer, Entity matching using large language models, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.11244>, ArXiv Preprint.
- [63] Q. Wang, Z. Gao, R. Xu, Exploring the in-context learning ability of large language models for biomedical concept linking, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.01137>, ArXiv Preprint.

- [64] J. Liu, Y. Chabot, R. Troncy, V.-P. Huynh, T. Labbé, P. Monnin, From tabular data to knowledge graphs: A survey of semantic table interpretation tasks and methods, *J. Web Semant.* 76 (2023) 100761, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.websem.2022.100761>.
- [65] J. Li, Y. Sun, R.J. Johnson, D. Sciaky, C.-H. Wei, R. Leaman, A.P. Davis, C. Mattingly, T.C. Wieggers, Z. Lu, BioCreative V CDR task corpus: A resource for chemical disease relation extraction, *Database* 2016 (2016) baw068, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/database/baw068>.
- [66] R.I. Doğan, R. Leaman, Z. Lu, NCBI disease corpus: a resource for disease name recognition and concept normalization, *J. Biomed. Inf.* 47 (2014) 1–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2013.12.006>.
- [67] M. Huijts, R.J. van Oostenbrugge, A. Duits, T. Burkard, S. Muzzarelli, M.T. Maeder, R. Schindler, M.E. Pfisterer, H.P. Brunner-La Rocca, Cognitive impairment in heart failure: Results from the Trial of Intensified versus standard Medical therapy in Elderly patients with Congestive Heart Failure (TIME-CHF) randomized trial, *Eur. J. Hear. Fail.* 15 (6) (2013) 699–707, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/eurjhf/hft020>.
- [68] M.L. Handoko, A.A. van de Bovenkamp, Cardiomems: the next revolution in heart failure management? *Neth. Hear. J.* 28 (1) (2020) 14–15, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12471-019-01356-2>.
- [69] M. Sung, H. Jeon, J. Lee, J. Kang, Biomedical entity representations with synonym marginalization, in: *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, ACL 2020, 2020*, pp. 3641–3650, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.335>.
- [70] Panacea Lab, OHDSI ananke: A tool for mapping between OHDSI concept identifiers and UMLS identifiers, 2024, <https://github.com/OHDSI/Ananke>. (Accessed 22 June 2025).
- [71] T. Kojima, S.S. Gu, M. Reid, Y. Matsuo, Y. Iwasawa, Large language models are zero-shot reasoners, in: *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, NeurIPS 2022, 2022*, p. 1613, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5555/3600270.3601883>.
- [72] N.F. Liu, K. Lin, J. Hewitt, A. Paranjape, M. Bevilacqua, F. Petroni, P. Liang, Lost in the middle: How language models use long contexts, *Trans. Assoc. Comput. Linguist.* 12 (2024) 157–173, http://dx.doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00638.
- [73] K. Järvelin, J. Kekäläinen, Cumulated gain-based evaluation of IR techniques, *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.* 20 (4) (2002) 422–446, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/582415.582418>.